

Rise of Women's Activism in Assam: A Study of the Pre-Independence Era

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Abstract:

The advent of American Baptist missionaries in Assam produced a very positive sociocultural environment since they tried to educate women along with their male counterparts in the region. No matter what their intentions were, it was good that they started teaching girls in Assam. Eventually it helped Assamese women in self-organization. Sevak Mahila Samiti, which was established in 1915 in Dibrugarh, was the first women's organisation of this region. Many such women's organisations were formed in the first part of the 20th century but they could not claim to have statewide focus. Assam Mahila Samiti was the first state-level women's organisation established in the year 1926. The growth of modern political consciousness among the Assamese people, including women, provided inputs for the rise of women's activism in this region. The Gandhian movement also played a significant role in growing political consciousness among women, which contributed towards the organisation of women in Assam. Assamese women made their public debuts through Mahila Samiti activities simultaneously with various activities of the freedom movement, despite the pervasive patriarchal beliefs and male biases in all walks of life.

Keywords: Women's Activism, Assam Mahila Samiti, Political Consciousness, Gandhian Movement, Chandra Prava Saikiani.

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Introduction

Women's activism has been an ongoing phenomenon in Assam since before India gained its independence. To explore the origin of women's activities in Assam one has to go back to the early part of nineteenth century. However, the year 1836 may be taken as the starting point for the exploration. The reason behind is that the American Missionaries who landed at Sadia in that year had immense inputs to the process of emancipation of Assamese women. It was Christian Missionaries who for the first time proposed educating women of Assam as in other parts of India. The paper tries to explore the socio-political activities of Assamese women in the pre-independence period through the activities of women's organizations like the Assam Mahila Samiti. It follows the qualitative method of research heavily based on secondary data collected from books, journals and newspapers.

Advent of the American Baptist Missionaries

Prior to the British occupation of Assam in 1826, formal education was exclusive to men of professional and learned sections and not to speak of women, it was not considered necessary even for the majority of men. The American Baptist Missionaries who came

along a printing press and a printer instituted the infrastructure of education for both male and female (Borpujari 8) heralding a new era in the culture and society of Assam. Initially, they were not successful at all in their effort to accommodate girls from upper caste at their schools as a result of which they started establishing girls' boarding schools where they gathered orphaned, destitute or abandoned girls. In the boarding school the girls were, however, segregated from the social environment. Although, the inner idea behind the policy of Missionaries to educate women along with male was to prepare them to be able Christian wives (Bora 9), this benefitted the Assamese society by producing extra ordinary Assamese Women personality namely, Chandra Prava Saikiani. Saikiani was, however, a product of Nagaon Mission Girls' School, run by American women Baptist Missionaries (Mahanta 92). She is said to be the founder of Women's Movement in Assam because it was her flesh and blood that worked behind the establishment of the Assam Mahila Samiti (later known as Assam Prodeshik Mahila Samiti), the first state level Women's Organisation in Assam in the year 1926.

Women's Organizations in Assam: The Prelude

The first record of a women's organization was that of the Sevak Mahila Samiti of Dibrugarh which was started about 1915. In a similar way around about 1916 the ladies of Sibsagar began a women's organization under the banner of Sibsagar Mahila Sanmilani. In her Mahila Samiti Ittbritti, Chandraprova Saikiani mentions her own involvement with the founding of two Mahila Samities in Nagaon and Tezpur in 1917 and 1919 respectively. There are records that Tezpur, which, like Nagaon, had a large Bengali and Brahmo Samaj presence and had a girls' primary school in the Bengali medium in the first decade of the twentieth century also had a Mahila Samiti prior to 1919 (Mahanta 98-100). However, the scope of these women's organizations was very limited and failed to make a statewide support base.

The Growth of Modern Political Consciousness

One of the most significant contributing factors towards the progress of women's activism in Assam through the development of women's organizations like the Assam Mahila Samiti was the growth of modern political consciousness among the Assamese people, including women (Mahanta 92-93). The spread of nationalist ideas in the latter part of the nineteenth century led to the growth of a new nationalist political consciousness among the Assamese people. The establishment of the Indian National Congress in 1885 had its indirect impact on Assam too, particularly through the activities of the Assamese students studying in Calcutta (now Kolkata). In 1889 the Assamese Students literary Society was formed in Calcutta. In 1903, the first modern political social organization in Assam, the Assam Association was formed under the leadership of a few educated and politically conscious individuals. Giving a new shape to social-political landscape in Assam, the first state conference of the association was held in 1905. In 1916, the Assamese students involved with the students' literary societies in Calcutta and other towns of Assam formed the Assam Chatra Sanmilan for cultural and educational purposes. In 1917, the first conference of a literary organization called the Assam Sahitya Sabha was organized in Sibsagar. All these organizations having as their aim the development of the Assamese people were interlinked, as more or less the same people joined in them. The annual conferences which were forums for discussion on all social and political matters involving the interest of Assamese people were often held in the same venue on consecutive dates, the organizers and participants going from one to the other. The deliberations of these conferences were confined to men. The president of the first conference of the Assam Chatra Sanmilan, organized in Guwahati in 1916 was Lakshminath Bezborua. The three young daughters of Bezborua were present at the conference and performed songs on stage. At a time when child marriage was the norm among upper castes and there were social prohibitions on women's appearing in public,

the presence of young educated girls in the conference created a sensation among the young students (Laksmidhar Sarma 9). Bezborua insisted that his wife accompany him to the Assam Association Conference the next day, since women had started attending the all-India Congress Sessions since Dr. Kadamini Ganguly had started the tradition in 1889 (Mahanta 94). Thus, with the acceptance of the presence of girls and women at these conferences began a new era in the socio-cultural history of Assam.

Being an educated and working woman, Chandraprova Saikiani took the opportunity to join the annual conferences of Assam Chatra Sanmilan and the Assam Sahitya Shabha as a delegate. The 3rd annual conference of Assam Chatra Sanmilan was held in Tezpur in the year, 1919. In this conference, Saikiani not only attended as a delegate but also delivered a lecture supporting a resolution proposed by Omeo Kumer Das on opium prohibition (Saikiani 2). This was recorded the first lecture delivered by a woman in front of a mixed audience in Assam. After the Tezpur event, she attended the third conference of Assam Sahitya Sabha which was held in the same year in Borpeta where Saikiani gave a speech on untouchability thus standing out among the other women delegates (Hazarika 27).

Assamese young educated women and schoolteachers like Lakshmipriya Chaliha, Purnya Prova Das, Chandrakanti Das and others also attended those conferences, but Saikiani bypassed them all by her extra-ordinary deeds. Chandra Prova Saikiani was the first woman in Assam to fight against the Purdah system prevalent at that time. Saikiani, who was present as a delegate at the Nagaon session of Assam Sahitya Sabha in 1925, aroused the ladies present in the meeting to break through the bamboo zenana fencing separating the ladies enclosure (Das 8-9).

As Saikiani emphasizes in her brief history of the Assam Mahila Samiti, entitled *Mahila Samitir Ittibritti* (The history of the Mahila Samiti), the formation and activities of nationalist organizations of Assamese people like Asom Sahitya Shabha, Assam Chatra Sanmilan etc. prepared the way for the emancipation of Assamese women in the form of Mahila Samities, by spreading awareness about the necessity and value of such organizations. Most women's participation in the conferences was usually that of passive observers. Although, after Chandraprova's example a few other educated women began reading papers or presenting recitations and songs at such conferences, their active participation was very limited as the educated women who could be delegates were few in number (Mahanta 95).

Gandhian Movement and Women's Activities

The Gandhian movement with its emphasis on women's political participation also helped in the rise of the women's activism in Assam (Mahanta 95-96). Particularly, arrival of Mahatma Gandhi in 1921 expedited the entire process on the part of women to pave the way to public by breaking the walls of private sphere in Assam. A great number of Assamese women were attracted by his charismatic leadership and impressive speeches that made them to come out in large number to take part in the programmes initiated by him in Assam along other parts of the country. In other words, the entry of Gandhi emerged as a new factor in socio-politico-cultural landscape of Assam, in general and in the sphere of women's lives, in particular.

Participation of Assamese people in the non-cooperation movement had begun before Gandhi's visit, but the special women's meetings he organized along with Begum Mahammed Ali, at every stoppage of his visit, encouraged the Assamese women, particularly those of the families of the Congress leaders to come out of their houses to participate in the movement. Nalini bala Devi, daughter of congress leader, Nabin Chandra Bordoloi recorded the activities of the ladies in Guwahati who contributed to the bonfires of foreign cloth or organized women's meetings encouraging the women to

spin yarn. Gandhi's call gave a momentum to the organisation of women of Assam by giving legitimacy to the idea of women leaving the home and participating in social and political activities such as attending meetings or picketing and even, at a later stage, going to jail.

In the absence of any women's organization and lack of general political consciousness at the time it was natural that the women belonging to the families of the prominent Congress leaders like the Chalihas in Sibsagar, the Agarwalas in Tezpur, of Torun Ram Phukan and Nabin Chandra Bordoloi in Guwahati should take the initiatives in organizing the women to come out of their homes. The foundation of the Assam Mahila Samiti can be seen against this background of new social and political activities among women (Mahanta 95-96).

As mentioned earlier, even before Gandhi appeared on the political scene of Assam, a few educated and conscious women had begun organizing themselves at local level. They organized primarily on the issue of women's education. Dibrugarh, founded by the British in 1849, where the first ladies' organization in Assam, namely, Sevak Mahila Samiti was formed was at that time the most progressive town in Assam. It was then a cosmopolitan town with tea, coal and oil industries nearby. It had the first railway line and a railway workshop in the province of Assam. Besides, it had a Government Boy's High School, the first government girls High school and the Berry White School, the first medical school in the entire region. A group of progressive peoples of the town formed a discussion forum called the Alochoni club sat weekly at the Amolapotty Nam ghar (Sarma, "Benudhar Sarma Rasanawali" 79). Women including Hemoprova Das, the headmistress of the girls' school also attended these meetings. This group of local ladies attending the weekly sittings at Amolapotty Nam-ghar along with their male counterparts organized themselves under the banner of Sevak Mahila Samiti with a view to encouraging women's education and rendering help to needy women (Boragohain 43).

Another ladies group called Sibsagar Mahila Sanmilani was formed in sibsagar, the former capital of the Ahom kings of pre-British times and first administrative center of the British in Upper Assam. It had the second government boy's school. The American Baptist missionaries set up their base here in 1840 starting schools for both boys and girls and started publishing the first Assamese journal, Orunodoi from the Sibsagar mission press. In 1914, a few educated young men thought of organizing the celebration of Joymoti Utsav (Joymoti festival) on the tithi (death anniversary) of Joymati Konwari. The goal behind this idea was to involve the women and awaken their nationalist sentiments. Accordingly the first Jymoti Utsav was held and was decided to make it an annual affair. Later the task of organizing this annual function was taken over by the ladies of the town. This was the purpose for which the Sibsagar Mahila Sanmilani was formed about 1916 (Saikiani 2).

Assam Mahila Samiti: The Ebb and Flow

None of these women's organizations could, however, gain statewide popularity and contribute to the organization of Assam Mahila Samiti. It was only the nationalist organizations of Assam like Assam Sahitya Sabha and Assam Chattra Sanmilan that provided the raw materials for establishing it and the support system so necessary for the fledging women's organization during the formative years. The founding meeting (held in Dhubri in 1926) and the three annual conferences of the Assam Mahila Samiti were held in the same venue as the annual conferences of the Assam Sahitya Sabha. Many of the educated women who were present with Saikiani in the Assam Chattra Sanmilan and Assam Sahitya Sabha conferences, like Punyaprova Das, Rajabala Das, Lakhpriya Kakaty were actively associated with the Assam Mahila Samiti from the very beginning (Mahanta 95).

The first Annual Conference of Assam Mahila Samiti held in Goalpara in October, 1927 was very well organized. Following on the decisions taken at the first conference an executive committee of the Assam Mahila Samiti was formed with Durgaprova Bora as president and Chandraprova Saikiani as secretary. The main work before the Assam Mahila Samiti was now to organize the local committees all over the state. To facilitate this Chandraprova Saikiani was appointed touring clerk on a commission of Rs.20/-. A number of resolutions were taken in this first annual conference under the president ship of Durgaprova Bora, who had the distinction of being the first lady matriculate of the state. The resolutions included condemnation of George Pilcher and Miss Mayo, condemnation of discrimination against an Assamese girl student at Calcutta Medical College, demand for amenities for women travelers in train and streamers, introduction of first aid classes in girls' schools, increase of girls' schools, application of local holiday list in missionaries (Mahanta 112-113).

Being a strong women's body of upper Assam, Sibsagar Mahila Sanmilani joined the Assam Mahila Samiti as its constituent branch in 1927. The Sibsagar Mahila Samiti under the leadership of Kanaklata Chaliha and Kamalaya Kakati thus, became an active branch of Assam Mahila Samiti. The Samiti organized a Shipini Bharal (weavers' collective) and started publishing Ghar Jeuti, the first women's magazine published in Assamese language. Besides, they organized regular meetings in outlying villages reporting such meetings in Ghar Jeuti. Later Ghar Jeuti started working as mouthpiece of Assam Mahila Samiti. Likewise, Branch Mahila Samities were formed throughout Assam. The Kamrup Mahila samiti was also a significant one. The body consists of a number of significant members namely, Nalinibala Devi, Swarnalata Saikia, wives of Dr. Bhubeneswar Boruah and Dr. Surya kr. Bhuyan and the like. They established a Sipini Bharal (weavers' collective) to help the poor women and began to work effectively to support the central Committee (Mahanta 113-114).

Prafullabala Choudhury, a descendant of the former Ahom King and the wife of writer Nagendra Narayan Chaudhury, presided over the second annual conference of the Assam Mahila Samiti, which took place in Jorhat in 1929. The main focus of discussion in this conference was on girls' education. Saikiani presented the statistics on female education in the state received from the district education offices, in which number of schools for girls, number students, ratio of male female teachers and funds spent on girls' education by local boards and municipalities was given. Since there were only three government-aided high schools for girls in the entire Assam Valley and Cotton College, the state's only college, did not admit women, she concentrated on the undervaluation of women's education and the absence of opportunities for them to pursue higher education (Mahanta 115).

The 3rd annual Conference of the Assam Mahila Samiti was organized in Golaghat district of upper Assam in the same year on 17-18, October, 1929. Narayani Handique presided over the meetings in this session. The noteworthy event of this session was the deliberation that took place on the newly passed Sarda Act and Gaur Act raising the age of marriage. In this session, after deliberation vote was taken and a resolution was passed supporting the implementation of the said acts. Being inspired by the spirit of the acts the members of Assam Mahila Samiti stopped a number of such marriages in Guwahati (Mahanta 120). Other resolutions were on education. One member of the Samiti proposed the resolution demanding compulsory primary education and education for girls (Mahanta 120).

Although, the Golaghat session was well attended, it happened to be the last conference of Assam Mahila Samiti. The undercurrents of tension also had negative impact on workings of the Mahila Samiti. People questioned why ladies had to attend meetings, one news paper reported apparently describing it a fish women's conclave (machar mel)

(Hazarika 27). But for Saikiani the more important thing than the outside barking was the tension within the Samiti due to the pull of conflicting forces of the different groups within the Samiti and their different conceptions of the functions and purposes of the Samiti. There was tension between the Guwahati group, centering Saikiani and the Upper Assam group, centering round the Ghar Jeuti group. The former was closer to the Assam Pradeshik Congress Committee and its political programmes while the later was more independent and stressed women's organization and issues of women's education and women empowerment. Chandraprova was close to Dr. Bhubaneswar Baruah and other congress leaders, on the other hand, Kanaklata Chaliha was the wife and Kamalalaya Kakati was the sister of Tara Prasad Chaliha, a Congress dissident (Bhuyan 10).

An anti Chandraprova faction arose among the delegates, particularly, from the upper Assam. Both the Dibrugarh and Sibsagar Mahila Samities were old Mahila Samities working independently for a long time. The Sibsagar Mahila Samiti in particular had a strong rural base and its chiefs, Kamalalaya Kakati and Kanaklata Chaliha organized meeting and published Ghar Jeuti successfully for two years. Since the Goalpara Conference, the Mahila Samiti head quarters and all members of the executive Committee was entirely Guwahati based to suit the secretary Saikiani's convenience, she herself living at that time in Bajali in Kamrup district. This must have irritated the Upper Assam Group particularly after they had successfully hosted the two latest conferences. The upper Assam Group, therefore, suggested that a new general secretary should be selected. Finally, it came to vote and Saikiani lost the election. Circumstances made Kamalalaya Kakati to be elected as joint secretary with Chandraprova under the condition that they would have equal power and work alternately. Although, Saikiani was satisfied with this attempt, the anti Saikiani faction demanded that the office be shifted to Sibsagar.

In the meantime, political situation also stood as an obstacle in the way of well functioning of the Assam Mahila Samiti. With the start of the Civil Disobedience movement in 1930, activists of the Mahila Samitis became totally involved in the freedom struggle. Punching a death blow to Assam Mahila Samiti, Saikiani was arrested and imprisoned for three months. In Sibsagar Kamalalaya kakati and Kanaklata Chaliha kept on publishing Ghar Jeuti till 1931, but were also involved in the movement moving through villages organizing meeting, encouraging the women to join in Satyagraha (Sarma, "Kongressar Kachiali Radat" 191). The Sipini Bharals set up by the Kamrup Mahila Samiti, the Dibrugarh Mahila Samiti, Sibsagar Mahila Samiti, Tezpur Mahila Samiti and others continued to function whereas, the Assam Mahila Samiti as an organization temporarily ceased to work (Mahanta 124).

Still, in 1934 and 1937, two conferences of Assam Mahila Samiti were organized in a very informal way in Guwahati. Although, the first one was held in its own pandal and the second one was held in the pandal of Assam Sahitya Sabha. The central theme of the first one was untouchability. However, the conferences failed to get back its past spirit and happened to be presided over by a male freedom fighter and religious leader, Pitambar Deva Goswami. In 1934 session, Saikiani stepped down as secretary after seven years and Rajabala Das became the secretary, with Durgaprova Bora continuing as president (Saikiani 9).

The absence of Chandraprova Saikiani contributed to the damage of the very skeleton of Assam Mahila Samiti. Saikiani tried to give the Assam Mahila Samiti back its original shape but in vain. With the entry of conservative lady like Rajabala Das, the Samiti, losing its original glory and popularity started digging its own cave. In this way, with the end of the saga of Assam Mahila Samiti, women's activism in Assam in its true spirit and vibrancy came to an end. The Mahila Samiti lived on, after 1945 with a new name, without having a strong backbone of its own.

Conclusion

The 1970s witnessed a new trend of women's activism in Assam with the formation of women's literary organizations like, Lekhika Samaroo Samiti, the Lekhika Santha etc. (Mahanta 1). Contesting the dismissive attitude of the male biased literary establishments towards women writers, these women's organizations have started a powerful movement against the male hegemony in social-cultural life of Assamese Society. The support and setting required for robust women's activities in Assam have also been provided by the Assam Movement and subsequent movements.

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